

Resolving Nigeria Public Policy Implementation Paradox: Due Diligence Is Sacrosanct

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Abstract

The imperative of prober implementation of public policy of a nation needs not to be over emphasized. One can say without any fear of contradiction that any nation or state where policy implementation is taken for granted relatively can hardly witness any progress to say the least. It follows that there exist an undeniable relationship between proper policy implementation and development. Why is it that public policy implementation unable to record remarkable success in Nigeria? The study examines policy in Nigeria and noted that it is an implementation paradox. Against the backdrop of the fact different administrations in Nigeria formulated series of lofty public policies but most cases, the success of this policies have been elusive due to poor implementation, abandonment, lack of coordination and no feedback mechanism, sectionalization, nepotism, primordial influences, ethno-religious bias, idiosyncrasy of policy formulator, egocentrism, selective and none implementation budget, misplaced priority, indiscipline and other issues are the paradox of public policy in Nigeria. The study suggest that adoption of due diligence is the catalyst to archiving lofty goals and objective for public policy implementation in Nigeria so that the aspiration of Nigeria government to impact better life for the citizens can become realizable.

Keywords: *Public, Policy, Civil Service, Paradox, Implementation.*

INTRODUCTION

The entity called Nigeria was born in the year 1914 as a British colonial construct, but after decades of colonial administration, attained independence in 1960 and republican status in 1963. Historically, the public service in Nigeria is a nurtured one, it began with the annexation and the need to adequately statellise and tie what become to aprons of the metropolis

The European staff were given discrepancy power to administer the colonies thereby determining what forms of shape the political, economic and social development assumed in the territories. It was not only that the state being in the hands of the colonial power, but that of a foreign rule allied with certain economic and political strata of the indigenous people which had interest in supporting colonialism. The reality all over the word, there are numerous problem confronting citizens. At the same time, the State is seen as a problem solving mechanism, while public policy is regarded as deliberate decision to act (or not) in response to societal problem (Johnson, 1991), Thus, the ecological and environmental factor organized by the colonial authority developed the public service into essentially civil service and quasi-government institution which were necessarily funded from financial sources the alien administrative structure of the British style took little recognizance of the social differentiation

while insisting that law and order must be maintained in addition to the manipulation of the public servant to mobilize resources to fund administrative cost.

However, from inception policy environment as most tedious problem suffer by third world countries like Nigeria range from policy imposition, hasty adoption of imported policies, lack of policy goals, and lack of social definition. It can be argued aptly that since independence Nigeria as recorded limited success in the area of public policy implementation. Owing to the fact that society is ordered, steered and directed towards deli red end of goals by the state through policies. Therefore, public policies play crucial roles in the state, in effect they are instrumental to the development and underdevelopment of any given state of course there are numerous policies initiated by different administrations in Nigeria since independence but the paradox of public policy implementation undermine the noble intention of both formulators and the policies. As a result of lack of due diligence.

Be as it may due diligence is a term used for a number of concept involving either the performance of an investigation of a business or person, or the performance of an act with a certain standard of law. It can be a legal obligation, but the term will more commonly apply to voluntary investigation. A common example of due diligence in various industries is the process with a potential acquire evaluates a target company or its asset for acquisition.

Originally the term linked to public offering of equity investments, but overtime it has come to be associated with investigation mergers and acquisition as well. The term has slowly been special e-mail lists. A closed-door meeting takes place in which it is decided that the accused has caused certain problems or committed violations or crimes. Evidence is said to have been produced, but the accused never knows what that evidence, exactly, was. A judgment is made in the accused's absence, and the poor accused individual becomes the last person to know about the conviction and sentence (which usually involves some deprivation of liberty. Such as ending or limiting that person's participation in a community, form or group). In some, there is no fair hearing, no right or self-defense by the accused against the accuser, and no adequate revelation of charges or reasons provided for consequent penalties. Some sort of trial takes place in which everything is wrong.

Given the dynamics and complexity of public policy process, as well as the unpredictable nature of actors and impact of the environment, public policy may not actually achieve the expected objectives because of lack of due diligence. It is for this reason it will enhance monitoring and evaluation of public policies and programmes become very expedient as to promote projects effectiveness, efficiency and its conformity to the original policy objectives during and after implementation. Due diligence and evaluation provide necessary feedback to improve the policy outcome and impact. It has been found out that the effectiveness of internal evaluation has been undermined in our society by the existence of overbearing bosses. Moreover the endemic nature of corruption as well as insecurity in the country, furthermore undermine the effectiveness of the public policy evaluation.

State of the Problem

In developing nations as Nigeria, the government often as to play the largest or certainly the lead role. Thus the national development plan declares that the federal government will occupy the commanding height in the quest for national development and provide the leadership an administration necessary to archive national objective via their policies. In our federal republic, this commanding heights be themed with the state government. Federal and state government together must assume not only major constructive roles in planning and

administering development programs through their policies, but in providing the infrastructure and services which enable private sectors to grow and prosper. Thus, the adequacy and effective implementation of public policy initiated will pave ways for the attainment for all the intentions of government at various levels towards the citizens. Admittedly public policies in Nigeria from independence have not recorded any remarkable success due to the implementation paradoxes that frustrated most of this policies even right away from the tables of formulators.

Objective of the Study

The main aim of this study, therefore is to critically examine public policy implementation in Nigeria. The imperative hinges on the fact public policy affect all and sundry, including academic, analyst, government and the public in general. Also the study will argue that public policy implementation is a paradox in Nigeria in view of the lofty public policies formulated and implemented over the years in the country

Conceptual Clarifications

Nigerian state: Nigeria is a product of British Colonial Construct and the state that was bequeathed was a capitalist state. Nigerian state like other capitalist states in the world promotes the interest of bourgeoisie (the ruling class). The country called Nigeria became a political independent country on 1st October 1960, but her economic, political, social expectation remain absolutely bleak. This premised on the fact that the laws and policies that emanate from the state reflects the interest of the dominant aim ruling, to the determinant of the teaming masses. This implies that state policies are always initiated to satisfy the interest of few privilege people and detrimental to the people purportedly exist to serve. Although, it is a well-known fact that Nigeria experienced long period of military dictatorship with its attendant slant and skewered practice of federalism. The de-federalization of the country probably accounts for what the new elite ascended power in 1999 failed to come to terms with any visible policy. However, politics or democracy cannot be separated from concept of rights, rule of law etc.it's about improvement in the living standard of the people. Admittedly, the support a democratically elected government enjoys from citizens apart from social security, political participation etc. is dependent on the enormous performance of the government measured in terms of employment generation, poverty reduction, access to primary healthcare, education, improve transportation, food security, adequate power supply etc that will emanate from government public policies. Following the critical performance evaluation of the Nigerian state, since inception of democracy in the country, several scholars and analyst have described the Nigerian state as exploitative, cruel and irresponsible (Ake 1981, Okowa 2005).

Put differently, Przeworki (1999) opens that the durability of the new democracies will depend, however, not only their institutional structure and the ideology of the major political forces hint also to a large extent in their economic performance. Profound economic reforms must be undertaken if there is to be any hope that the deterioration in living condition experienced by many democratic country will ever seize. In line with above submission Diamond (1997) posit that it is a truism that the better performance of a democratic regime in producing and broadly distributing improvement in living standard, the more likely it is to endure.

However, prejudice to the poor performance of the past military regime in economic development and management and despite the lofty promises and good intentions that must have informed the General Abdusalami Abubakar's agenda certain broadcast of July 1998 on

assumption of official Nigerian military head of state, as stated inter. We intend in the limited time at our disposal to take infant and decisive steps to bring relief to our people. We shall implement short-term macro-economic measures targeted at specific sectors whose revitalization would have multiplier effect on the economy, productive activities, household income and purchasing power. Consequently, on all these lofty promises, poverty becomes merely visible in Nigerian state.

Obvious from the inception of fault republic, there are demonstration of commitment, faithfulness and dedication on the path of the civilian regime to run a government characterized by conducive environment attractive to foreign investors and enhance good government based on equity, fairness, justice, transparency, accountability and devoid of corruption, nepotism and political manipulation of our public institution. However, the first term in office of Obasanjo's civilian regime (1999 – 2003) and even successive administration no significant has being made in achieving the lofty aim and objectives embedded in public policies initiated of the regimes. There have been high record and wide spread allegations of looting of government treasury, misappropriations, rent seeking and outright embezzlement of public funds. Instead, there have been unprecedented capital flight from the country in the past decade. Poor implementation of public policies representable for all these maladministration in Nigerian state. The policy, rather than being an effective antidote has since its implementation been an unmitigated disaster for the working masses and the economy in funeral (DSM, 2003)

Public policy: public policy and politics, if it could be added, are two inter-related concepts. The term policy does not bend itself to easy definition. In-fact, it has been observed that no concept in social science parlance has suffered more ambiguity and abuse deriving from the many context in which it employed that public policy (Jackson & Jackson 2001). A policy, weather public or private is a cause of action or general plan adopted or pursued in response to a given circumstance or pursue an objective in a given state (Agagu, 2010). Public policy can thus be seen as an intention, pronouncement, a general plan or action adopted by a government to solve a social problem counter a threat, deal with a given circumstance or pursue an objective in a given state. the inclusion of intension and pronouncement may appear out of place because they are sometimes amorphous yet, there is need to note that the pronouncement of a king may have the force of law and his intentions may guide the directions of his pronouncement and law, for example the pronouncement of president Bola Tinubu oil subsidy removal took immediate effect and change the price of pump price.

In the same vein bye (1975) described public policy as what government chooses to do and not to do. Further that, government do many things. They regulate conflicts within society, they organize society to carry on conflicts with other society and they distribute a great variety of symbolic reward and material services to members of the society and extract money from the society, most at times in the form of taxes. Thus, policies may regulate behaviour, organize bureaucracies, distribute benefits and extract taxes or all of these things at once. Basically, public policies are meant to provide, control, protect, distribute, redistribute, and promote values and services among others. Edward (2004) posits that essentially, the objective of policy is to make the response of the agency or body in charge predictable and fear to all affected citizens.

The plethora of problem confronting the citizens, the state, the citizen-state relations, and the institutions and actors for accomplishing government goals have combined to make the notion of public policy a multi-faceted phenomenon. Different government place different values on each purpose. Invariably, these differences are reflected in their public policies.

Furthermore, the commitment to these policies, the expertise and analysis brought into them play significant role in their success. Underlining this is the nature of politics and the ecological factors propelling it.

It is imperative to analyze the two broad streams that involved in public policy. The first is the public policy making process and implementation, of which it's more descriptive rather than prescriptive. This can be categorized along six emphasis, elitism, groups, systems, institution, non-institutionalism and organized anarchy, which falls under the descriptive orientation (Henry, 1999). Second stream prescribe ways to improve the content of public policy by improving the ways public policy is made. In this context, models of the instrumentalism, rationalism and the strategic planning readily comes to mind, which are prescriptive biased. Away from theoretical postulations and model, ordinarily in an ideal terms and reference public policy making process is divided into different phases, which rightly includes problem identification, policy initiation, deliberation and formulation, implementation and the policy evaluation stages accordingly. (Darki and Kimiebi 2011). Further that, the adopted policy is only a statement of intensions, expectations, directions and hopes. Therefore, most public policies require activities and enforcement mechanisms to effectuate them, they are basically formulated public by authorities. These implies that those persons, who engage in the daily affairs of a political system, are recognized by the most members, so long as they act within the limits of their roles (Anderson, 1975). Hence, Geston (2004) submits that public policy arena is fraught with confusion, contradictions and consternations. The inference that can be drawn from above is that public policy even in advanced countries faces some challenges, through over the years, they have devised means of coping with them. Furthermore, the patriotism and dedication of the policy actors in such countries to national and human development have been able to ensure public policy stability. It is of note that public policy-making process in Nigeria often exhibit erratic turn. A survey of the various aspect of Nigeria's public life since independence portends a state of pathology considering the education industry to other sectors such as health, economy, agriculture, defense, transportation, housing, environment, judicial decisions, executive orders and rules government budgets, local ordinances, foreign relations and others. All these are concerns and activities of government as they affect a large spectrum of issues and sectors of the society.

Implementation of Public Policy-Civil Services Nexus

The civil service remains pivotal in any government. Its level of performance in the discharge of its primary functions of articulation and implementation of government policies to a very large extent. Admittedly, the Nigerian civil service derived its origin from colonial administration. It has remain central as a vehicle for achieving government objectives from its original conception as a collaborative instrument for exploitation for the imperialist administration through various administrations and regime types has undergone structural and attitudinal reforms to cope with the visions, aspirations and goal of successive administrations.

There is no doubt that after 1960 the role of the public service particularly the civil service was considerably expanded as an 'agent' for re-ordering socio-political change in addition to embryonic supporting functions for the governing political-class, consequently helping to rank order national priorities through advices to the political class as well as perform political socialization functions for the same political class. From the onset, the unified function which the civil services ought to perform was weakened because it is structured into two: the generators and the technicians. While the generators were to perform responsibilities of nitrating politics, the technical pattern were to execute such policies. Although this

arrangement was not bad in itself the two were made to disrupt each other and therefore had to operate from two different parameters, this was fundamental that the two could not produce leadership roles.

Consequently, the civil service that was developed and monitored during colonial era was essentially organized not tally to service the interest of the colonial authority but the very public servants who were keen in accumulation of private property using their important position and the manipulation of the quasi-institutions such as public cooperation to divert funds into private companies. The role of civil service in aiding development, mobilizing the rural masses and improving productivity for national development was recasted and turned to service the private companies. Therefore, the leadership responsibility which civil service ought to have played in the society became an illusion insofar as the civil servants become more concerned with sectional interest and accumulation of private wealth to the detriment to the welfare of the general populace.

Of course, the civil service between 1960-1966 could not provide leadership role to assist and fasten the pace of national development not necessarily because it had if the tool to realize this goal, but because of other factors apart from the above. One of such factors was the issue of aggressive ethmaty or sometimes called competitive modernization. The public servants whether political masters civil servants and those in the government quasi-institutions having come from different ethnic groups saw their different ministries, political offices and parastatals as in curative pipes where ethnic interest were could be aggregated. One consequence was the persistent struggles between the elites of each ethnic groups in an attempt to control of such government institutions in the sixties, leadership and development therefore was conceptualized in terms of how much contract, wealth or jobs were made available to one's ethnic group. The dangerous implication therefore was that the interest of the nation was submerged particularly, then the ethnic consciousness came to determine the unity between the civil servants, politicians and other servants in the parastatals.

To a large extent the activities of civil servants between 1960 and 1966 in the initiation of public policy did not focus on providing the leadership the society required, rather, Granitic efforts were made to manipulate all the state institutions to pursue cooperate class interest and the promotion of regional developments.

Although, at some form of symbiotic relation pervaded between the civil service, parastatals and the military it was evident that such relationship were somehow temporary because to a large extent the civil servants conditioned and determined what was planned when and how they were executed and who get, what, when and how, essentially because of their private interest. The emerging indigenous property class has the civil service as a Condit pipe through which it could obtain public funds inform of contracts etc. The degree of leverage the civil servants exerted on politicians; or crop of which belong to this propertised class became more conspicuous by 1962 using the marketing boards and other parastatals to exploit public funds, thereby relegating the general welfare of the citizens, to the background. (Egwunube, 1986).

Be as it may, civil servant perform the following functions towards implementation of policies and running of government. Amidst the underlined functions of civil servants are that they provide policy formulations, policy implementation, policy execution, advice to governments, intermediary roles, provision of social services, budget preparation, law enforcement, enlightenment functions, delegated legislations such as making rules, regulations,

and bylaws, provision of employment opportunities, and other routine functions such as document keeping, collection of taxes, answering letters and preparing bulletin, representing the executive in public functions and in other meetings.

Aside this sundry rules, the civil servants roles cannot be divorced from the political, institution and economic development of the country.

Aforementioned, during the colonial era, the civil service was mainly concerned with the maintenance of law and order and the existence of a peaceful climate suitable to the colonial masters (Olagunju, 2002). After the independents, the emphasis was on social and economic development, and with the infusion of the military, the civil service got exposed to function incompatible with its traditional roles.

During this period, the military suspended the constitution and rule by decree. Since, the military lacked the administrative acumen, they turned to the civil servants hence their roles changes, a lot of power came to their procession, they did not only become proud, they became corrupt and discovered the sweetness of power and influence of politics; thereby killing the neutrality features of civil service. For example, during the Gowon administration at federal level, the civil servants were allowed to attend Federal Executive Council, and to speak on issues. It was the era of super-permanent secretaries and its politicization, changing to Director-General before it was reversed to the statues quo.

On slightly different dimension, Obasi (1985) argues that in a political system, where a progressive ideology is non existing it is not the public service that will be weak but the national economy which is also subject to the shackles of imperialist manipulations. Seemingly further expansion of internal colonialism conditioned by the political class, the civil servants and other groups could contribute to derailing the paths of development. In political leadership and a progressive ideology and lacking the public service has been greatly weakened to perform its sacred duties if improving the materials condition of masses. This was evident in 1979 and 1983 because the public service itself particularly the civil servants who were expected to guide the politicians were themselves in real politics could not perform such roles.

Although, they might not have shown their party cards ordering it was a known fact that, they effectively struggled for power, territories for sphere of influence, for supremacy for personal benefits and for benefits for a wide range of clients who had come across them (Egwurube, 1986).

Policy Implementation and Due Diligence

Public policy implementation is the act and process of converting a policy into reality or simply enforcing the policy. That is, it is the process of translating policy mandate into actions, and policy goals into reality. Implementation process consist of putting it to active action organization, the socio political and economic environment, the policy target group, objectives the enumerated method of implementation and the political resources (Sharkansky and Meter, 1995). It hopes that by concentrating of programme, as well be realized (Pressman and Widausky, 1979).

This terms from the fact that vague and contradicting policies are difficult to implement. Furthermore, the issue of where implementation start from and where it ends is not a settled matter (Ingram, 1992). Obvious in the policy implementation in Nigeria as rightly described Agagu, (2010) posits that in Nigeria, many of the public policies are inter-governmental in nature giving the fact that many of the policies are often initiated by the federal government.

While analyzing implementation of rural development in Nigeria between 1988 and 1983 elsewhere Agagu (1995) employed an eight variable cluster used by Van Horn and Van Meter (1977). These variables include policy resources; policy standards communications; enforcement; disposition of the implementers, characteristics of implementing agencies; political environment; and economic and social conditions. It was found out that these variables greatly affect the outcomes of public policy implementation in Nigeria. Synergism of due diligence in view of implementation come to play. The idea of due diligence is very well established in mainstream culture and society. In fact it has been established in all concept of modern democracy ever since the modern democracy developed. It has been observed that legal systems and agents of the state often do things to undermine due diligence. And why we might say evaluative mechanisms sometimes balancelly violate its, but the concept itself is considered quite legitimate in all corners of legal argument, it is not by any means, a radical or utopian idea. This manifest where there is no room for communication between the policy implementers and the general public that the initiated policies will eventually affects in all ramifications. Here there is no regard for public opinions through which the government can receive proper and adequate feed-backs of the policies initiated by them and implemented by their agencies. Unfortunately, once we look at the conduct of many egalitarian collectives, due diligence begin to look like idea. This is an irony that truly puzzle us. Because egalitarian collectives are supposed to build upon the basic concepts of democracy and strife to make things more democratic. The people within this collectives are supposed to view the basic standards of fairness within convectional society as being relatively minimal compared to those of the society that we all want to build. Meanwhile the tenets of democracy include freedom of speech and open opportunity to contribute to decision-making process through their representatives but this vital opportunities are missing in Nigeria brand of democracy. This accounts for the absence of constitutional rules often leaves the policy menu open, leaving the flaps to be filled in an ad hoc manner. This is obvious of civilian government in Nigeria where there is constitution to guide the activities of public office-holders. However, because of the absence of spirit of constitution, people have mastered how to circumvent its letters. Kalu (2004) argued quite correctly that the absence of an established policy framework has created avenues for mismanagement of public resources with no mechanism for holding public officials responsible for their roles in government. However, there are probably many specific examples of the violation of due diligence in handling government crucial projects and programmes in Nigeria and people go array with it without being reprimanded and take place within collectives. None the less it would be advantageous for existing collectives to address the most obvious and immediate problems, that is, egalitarian collectives are it to themselves and others to pursue important principles such as due diligence in public policy implementation in more advance ways than convectional society, rather than acting as though they are ignorant of the conventions of justice that most people already recognize. However, absence of due diligence in public policy implementation ,may results to situation of government and their agencies losing credibility if they don't protect the civil liberties of their citizens. In every democratic world egalitarian and collectives, where people might have particularly strong desires to right certain wrongs found within their society.

Addressing the dearth of due diligence in own country and communities, these attempt will probably expose a few lapses in the policy implementations, becoming more skilled and articulate in advocating for the evaluation mechanism, communications and feed-back mechanisms in Nigerian policy implementation. If this trails of basic principles of due diligence

are missing at the same time that due diligence is being stifled in the mainstream community, then the outcome might not be so good.

Public policy implementations is the Achilles in the public policy making process. In reality, good policies go away during implementation. This is because of the effect of a number of intervening variables such as the nature of the bureaucracy and other institutions, various groups competing for value and resources, types of ruling elite and the orientation, ideology, parasitic god fathers, among other things. All these factors along its objectives and the clarity to the implementers as well as the strategies adopted along and the policies resources greatly affects the outcomes of the policies (Agagu, 2005).

The Implementation Paradox

Nigeria is benefit of an appropriate ideology capable of bringing about authentic national development and integrative political system in the country. Granting also that capitalism, mixed economy, welfarism or whatever that is today paraded as Nigeria is true ideology exist, but the basic argument against it is that it has failed to produce development in the country. Rather, it has determined the path of Nigeria's underdevelopment and deserves nothing but change. Presently, Nigeria is swimming in the ocean of abject poverty, absence of basic amenities and excruciating underdevelopment, not because, there are no good public policies to ameliorate the situation, but simply premise on poor policy implementation. It is obvious that, if all the policies formulated in the country over the years were implemented accordingly, no doubt, Nigeria would have been on a fast lane of development. However, it is a paradox that most of this public policies exist only on paper and never implemented to actually manifest, their goals and objectives for which they are formulated. The culture of public policy abandonment is therefore in a very high degree in Nigeria and virtually account for failure of levels of government. Gen. Olusegun Obasanjo military regime initiated operation feed the Nation (OFN) to boost administration led by Sheu Shagari, he initiated Green Revolution to replace OFN that established to perform function, later Agricultural Development Strategy, and this was unable to arrest the massive importation of food. ADP that was originally meant to meet the needs of small-scale farmers, more often than not, benefited the large scale farmers. The River Basin Authority, on the other hand, has led to measure dislocation of the poor farmers as a result of the reconstruction of dams and irrigation land. a case in point is that of Bakabri where hundreds of displaced peasant families were massacred by the mobile police squad on Saturday 26th April, 1980 for daring to complain of inadequate and even lack of compensation for the land and properties they lost (Abba, 1985). Admittedly, this culture of non-implementation of public policies is therefore has since become the norm of a recurrent dermal in our country normal life. Public policies have become a mere rhetoric with no iota of commitment.

Overview of the constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria since 1999 reflected unrealizable aspirations on the part of public policy goals. For example, chapter II contains the fundamental objectives and directive principles of state policies section in which are the political objectives and 15 (5) states that the state shall abolish all corrupt practices and abuse of office. Section 16 contains the economic objectives and 16(2) states that states shall draft its policy towards ensuring that (d) That suitable and adequate shelter, suitable and adequate food, reasonable national minimum wage, old age care and pension, and unemployment, sick benefit and welfare of the disabled are provided for all citizens. These have become just mere declaration of intent which the ruling parties in various tiers of government in the country fail to respect and adhere to. Thus, the implementation paradox of

public policy in Nigeria is multidimensional. This study shall identify and explain some of them.

Lack of Commitment and Direction of Implementation

Over the years, civil servants (implementers of public policy are directly or unconsciously serving the regimes rather than the people). This has become more relevant in the Fourth Republic. But what has been the relationship between public bureaucracies in Nigeria since independence, the Nigerian civil service had continued to serve the masters without any attention to the relationship between it and the government. This has made it to continue play political roles. Thus, the perception, interest, strategies of bureaucracy and action became a determinant factor in shaping public policy interest looking at the goals and objectives of the policy.

This leads to assertion that if government in most African countries have been repressive, and poly not reliable, as many observers believe, the civil servant (bureaucracy) has been a major partner if not the sole actor in the game. The situation in Nigeria today is that bureaucracy has grown so large that it has become isolated from the people. It has become irresponsible to the needs of the people to the extent that it can no longer be influenced by public opinion.

Lack of political Will

When policies are formulated, their operational capability is made to coincide with the condition that necessitate their creation. So from inception the policy seems to be designed more as a showpiece, rather than functional instrument. To buttress this point, notice that the spare of corruption perpetrated during the military interregnum in spite of the creation of the corruption practices Act.

Yet the way the act has been designed, there is nothing in it to enable the body with the execution of the law to bring to book all those who committed identifiable corrupt practiced prior to some 13,2000 and up to date, the day the law came to force. The consequences of the law that lack retroactive power is a creation of negative impression that some people are above the law. However, once the impression is created that law does not respect whosoever, other people begin to perceive the law as something that cannot be breached.

The argument is that, even though the set objectives of government policies or laws meant to benefit the public, the cabal that holds the top echelon of government hostage, at any point in time, will jeopardize or frustrate the implementation of public policies or laws. In the energy sector for instance, Nigeria with a population of over 140million people presently generates only a miserable 1, 800 mega watt capacity. And despise the seeking of a copious 13.2 billion US dollars in the sector by Olusegun Obasanjo regime between 1999-2007, no tangible result was achieved (Egbujuyi, 2009).

Discontinuity in Policy

This factor is associated with frequent and abrupt changes in the political leadership of the country and the propensity of every new administration to chant a totally new direction in policy choices. But given (a) the role of the civil service in policy advisement and (b) its relative stability regardless of changes in political leadership, it is the judgment of this study that serious discontinuity in policy would not have risen if the leaders of the service were themselves communed of the appropriateness of the choices made in the first instance.

Law and Falling Morale

Law and falling morale a distinctive to high productive is associated with the purge of the civil service of deed words and corrupt official begun in 1975 and carried further in 1984 and the consequent sense of insecurity indicated on many of civil servant. There is hardly any basis for this development, given the good intentions of every house-cleaning exercise, and if civil servants are indeed good at their jobs and are above board. There is no basis for disputing the Biblical verdict that the diligent workman would stand before kings and not before mean men.

Corruption

Corruption is perceived as any decision, act or conduct that subvert the integrity of people in authority or effectiveness in performing its assigned roles (Lodge, 1998). Put differently it is the unsanctioned or unscheduled use of public resources for private ends (Leveine, 1975).

Lodge further sees it as acts that are intentionally dishonest which might take of non-performance of a recognized duty, or the unwarranted exercise of power, with the motive of gaining some advantages more or less personal. Political corruption, however, can be defined as method of exploitation by which a constituent part of the public sphere exploited as if it were part of the market spheres (Sandan, 2007).

A broader definition of political corruption includes electoral fraud as well as rewarding political parties of specific constituencies in return for electoral support. This has been a major issue in the politics of public policy implementation in Nigeria when corruption penetrated the implementation process, public policies become mutated and the desired goal may not be achieved.

Most public policies are formulated and funds appropriated for, but corruption like an octopus has continued to entangle, ruin and make impossible the implementation process. However, due to corruption, Nigeria is still under the instance, the sum of 50 billion naira was allocated to the National Poverty Eradication by Obasanjo administration, but paradoxically, the level of poverty instead of decreasing is rather the increase. Due to the fact that the money was converted to private ends, hence frustrating the implantation process.

Manifestation of corrupt transactions range from acceptance of money or other rewards for awarding contracts, violations procedures to advance interests, including kick-back from development programme or multinational cooperation's, pay-off for legislative support and intervening in the justice process. Forms of corruption also include nepotism, common theft, overpricing, establishing non existing projects, pay roll padding and collection and tax assessment frauds, from this perspective, the notion of corruption be broadened (Sandan, 2007).

Poor Remuneration

This is cited in comparative context that is with respect to the private sector of the economy for identical positions of responsibility. Its effect on the civil servants in the depression of the urge to exert maximum efforts at work. However, it does not appear that this factor can still be seriously sustained in view of the improvements in the civil service remuneration package and such intangible but significant prestige which civil servants enjoy over and above the rest of society.

Inadequate executive Capacity

This factor refers to shortfalls (largely unanticipated) in the projected magnitude of skilled manpower required to accomplish planned policy objectives. It has variously been seen as a cause of the underfulfilment of most public policies in Nigeria.

Hasty Adoption of Public Policy

Unnecessary haste in the adoption of public policies in Nigeria always result to implementation paradox. It is as if government alone knows everything about the people and the society. Policy making becomes devoid of policy analysis as well as implementation analysis. It is therefore not surprising that many of public policies in Nigeria end up in confusion and failure. Many a times, public policies implementation are often subjected to whims and caprices of the chief executive, or its associates. This implies that there is no commitment towards the policy implementation and it results to abandonment.

Misplaced priority

Most public policy in Nigeria are squarely a reflection of the personal interest of the political class or a times some are initiated to satisfy political patronage rather than the demand of the citizens, as such policies lack public support in terms of implementation. This is attributed to lack of political sensitivity. Experience has shown and there is no doubt that most public policies that are hurriedly executed in the country turn out to be misplace priority.

The motive behind them are implemented based on what the implementing officials stands to benefit from the process. For instance in Ekiti presently, the community are in need of link roads, portable water while government engage in overhead bridge.

Sectionalism and ethnic Biases

Sectionalism aim ethnicity has also continued to mar public policy implementation. Experience has shown that some national policies implemented fully in some parts of the country, but simply abandon or marginally implemented in other areas. For instance the school feeding that gained a very high momentum in the northern part of Nigeria, did not spread to the southern part the same time. Another instance occurred in the health sector, when the former Yobe state Commissioner for health, Dr. Mammn Mohammed said drugs and other consumable worth over #7,528billion supplied by the PTF to the state in 2003, under the Bamako initiative scheme expired and became useless before they were sold, as they were more than what the stat required. He went further to state that the yearly drug requirement of the state is #1.million only, but PTF supplied a total of about #198billion worth of drugs and hospital consumables to about ten General Hospitals in Yobe state between 2001-2003 (Etekpe,2007). Juxtaposing the yobe stat experience with the Niger delta and south east states of the federation reveals that those areas suffer from gross inadequacy in the supply of drugs, but Yobe state was simply favoured because the chief implementation officer was from the Northern extraction. (Paki and ebienfa, 2011).

CONCLUSION

In the study, the issue of public policy implementation paradox in Nigeria was extensively analyzed, where qualitative research method was used and data was obtained from texts, publications, journals, newspapers and personal observation. The study examined various concepts such as the Nigerian state public policy where iterative on each concept were reviewed. Obviously in Nigerian state, there it was discovered that the state has been under

‘Serge’ from inception because of conflicting political wills of leaders premised on religious and ethnicity differences. Further, it was noted that Nigerian state is oppressive, armed, irresponsible, weak, exploitative and lack of autonomy. With all narrative of description, made it so difficult for Nigeria to witness successful implementation of public policies.

The study conclude further that public policy implementation in Nigeria will remain a dream never come true with the presence of these paradoxes, corruption, sectionalism and ethnic biases, misplaced priority, hasty adoption of public policy, poor remuneration, low and falling morale, discontinuity in policy, lack of political will and others. The paradox highlighted above hinder the implementation of Nigeria public policies in the past years and present.

Therefore, the study suggest that until public policies are implemented to achieve the lofty goals for which it was initiated, the general aspiration of Nigeria becomes one of the developed countries will be unrealizable.

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